

UNDERSTANDING EXPERIENCES OF SENIOR HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS OF INTEGRATED PUBLIC SCHOOL DURING NEW NORMAL: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL INQUIRY

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Abstract: The study's goal was to discover more about the life stories of the Senior High School students from Integrated Public School of Alabel 1 District, Division of Sarangani, during the new normal. This study utilized a holistic phenomenological study design to understand the experiences of Senior High School students in Integrated public schools during the new normal for the School Year 2020-2021. The researcher chose six (6) participants from grades 11 and 12 to undergo in-depth interviews using the validated questionnaire. This study used the Key Participants' Interview Approach to gather the needed data. The study findings revealed that the learners' viewed the new normal as challenging, optimistic, and an opportunity. As to the feelings, they found the new normal created negative, positive, and mixed emotions, which were the combination of positive and negative emotions. Meanwhile, the Senior High School experienced a positive impact on time freedom and independence and a negative effect on learning and behavior of the new normal in the education setting among Senior High School learners.

Keywords: Educational management, COVID-19 pandemic, integrated public school, new normal education, modular learning, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Coronavirus disease spread quickly in 2019, resulting in a global pandemic that has claimed millions of lives thus far. To date, this unprecedented health emergency has taken a toll on the economy of millions of individuals and families. The pandemic has also impacted the educational systems of many countries as it forced educational institutions, and as a result, learners globally become affected.

With this global crisis, learners encountered difficulties in various areas, including teaching and learning experiences, student achievement, and faculty perspectives. Students' experiences and perspectives toward different learning modalities are particularly significant because they are ultimately the foundation of curriculum adjustment. Further, not only the academics are affected but also the life itself, for instance, the well-being, physical, mental, emotional, and other aspects (Zalat, Hamed and Bolbol, 2021).

Indeed, the "New Normal Education" is a big challenge for students. The unique circumstances presented for Senior High School students require an inquiry through an academic lens to better understand the phenomenon. The term new usual first appeared in 2018. The term "financial crisis" refers to the dramatic economic, cultural, and social transformations that

caused insecurity and social unrest, influencing collective notions and personal ways of life (Buonerba, Ballesteros, Choo, Hasan, Korshin and Naddeo, 2021; Brown, Vostok, Johnson, Burns, Gharpure, Sami and Laney, 2021).

Unquestionably, due to the outbreak of COVID-19, students from the Integrated Public School of Alabel 1 District, Division of Sarangani, were obliged to isolate themselves at home to prevent the virus from spreading. The area is particularly far-flung from the metro and much more so from the nation's capital, resulting in a significant difference in experiences regarding the modes of learning. The new normal has a detrimental effect on student's mental health, resulting in frustration, stress, and depression. In studies investigating the difference in academic performance of Senior High School students at Fort Valley State University, there is no significant difference between online and face-to-face learning (Paul and Jefferson, 2019).

In Sarangani, most schools use asynchronous learning, referred to as active learning, in which schoolchildren learn and develop. Despite this, it remains unclear how the new state of education affects students' learning experience Inguva (2021). explains that the premise of online learning is learning in different times and spaces. Teachers focus on providing learners with learning resources such as modules, booklets, handouts, and materials like books to help them learn independently.

Indeed, teachers played a significant role throughout the year, and they had difficulty keeping class focus, especially at the elementary school level. However, the new normal has added a new layer to the problem, especially for teachers assigned in far-flung areas as a Learning Support Aide at Banlibato Integrated School for six months. The researcher believes that the crisis of COVID-19 presents new experiences for teachers in the new educational environment.

In fact, in the locale of the study, based on the academic performance of the Grade 11 learners for the school year 2019-2020, they got an average grade of 85 in the third quarter, while they got only 80 average grades in the fourth quarter. Looking at the data, we can say that learners encountered the problem of transitioning to the new normal. Further, this result might indicate that the learners are struggling with the limited access to resources like the internet, books, and gadgets, and the teacher and parents' support they need.

From this lens and the previous literature mentioned, the researcher would like to explore the experiences of senior high school students in an integrated public school during the new normal. Precisely on the challenges encountered learners' coping mechanisms and the impact of the new normal in the learning of Grade 11 and 12 learners.

Purpose of the Study

Relative to advancing the educational scheme in addressing the emerging problems in learning in an age of the new normal, this study was crafted to explore the experiences of the Senior High School students in three integrated public schools of Alabel 1 District, Division of Sarangani.

This study only focused on the in-depth understanding of the experiences of the Senior High School students in the mentioned district during the new normal; thus, the generalization of the impact of the pandemic on the experiences of senior school students in another school would not be applicable in this study.

Personal in-depth interviews at home were employed among key participants to get the vital information needed without biases. Participants answered all questions thoroughly during the discussion.

The student's personal experiences were presumed, as they served as the primary output in the analysis stage. The student's personal experiences contributed significantly to developing a solution that would aid them in generating recommendations for the study's problem.

Research Questions

1. How do the senior high school students view their experiences in the new normal?
2. How do the senior high school students feel about their experiences during the new normal?
3. How does the new normal impact the learning experiences of senior high school students?

Theoretical Lens

This study was anchored by Zimmerman (2002) that the fundamental concept associated with Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) is the importance of self. He proposed a three cyclical phase model of SRL, which involves the idea of self in terms of forethought, performance, and reflection. Self-motivation and task-analysis processes such as goal setting and strategic

planning are included in the first phase. Self-control and self-observation are required during the second phase, implementation.

In support of this theory, Winne's (2005) Four Turning Points Model specifies learning behaviors in each of the three cyclical phases. The Four Turning Points Model suggests critical processes or turning points during SRL. The model further proposes that learners must understand the learning environment (Turning Point 1). This turning point requires a learner to understand academic success factors such as time requirements, expectations, and environmental influences.

Meanwhile, Winne suggested that Goal setting (Turning Point 2) can only proceed once Turning Point 1 is satisfied. Turning Point 2 requires a learner to identify the academic goal and begin developing strategies for achieving that goal.

Learning strategies (Turning Point 3) require a learner to have or be able to obtain the necessary skills to implement learning strategies. It can only occur once Turning Points 1 and 2 are satisfied. When all turning points are satisfied, the learner must also be motivated to spend the time and effort necessary to apply the learning strategies (Turning Point 4).

However, Winne stated that tools and technologies could only support SRL if they had been designed and implemented for that purpose. Also, students and teachers must have the skills and motivation to use digital technologies. In this regard, online instructional design and delivery require additional consideration compared to traditional face-to-face learning environments.

In connection to the study, these theories, the Self-Regulated Learning (SRL), Four Turning Points Model, and Web-Based Technologies (WBTs), are essential aspects of learning and achievement in academic contexts. Self-regulating students are much more likely to succeed in school, learn more, and achieve higher levels. With the concept pointed in these theories would be the same theories that the learners should consider in learning in the new normal, where teachers' presence is not visible, and they need to know on their own. The researcher supported the proposition that during this new normal, students were forced to study blended learning like online or modular learning, with reduced access to facilities and less interaction with teachers and peers, but also have more freedom in doing school activities.

As an educator, the researcher believed that by using an individual differences approach, students could adapt to emergency remote learning, concentrating on resource management techniques and signs of successful adaptation to emergency remote learning. Before the crisis, students are less able to regulate their attention, effort, and time and be less motivated; they also had reported investing more time and effort in their self-study.

Significance of the Study

Senior High School students from various grade levels and integrated public schools benefit from and the drawbacks of the new learning despite the ongoing pandemic throughout the country. This study has taught us to appreciate the students' unique viewpoints on their diverse environments and socio-economic condition. They discussed their pleasant and unhappy experiences to provide us with the findings to complete this research report. Despite the new educational system's negative consequences on students, each response demonstrated their commitment to complete the school year by utilizing their incentive to work harder.

Thus, this research aims to make available to the general public the experiences and viewpoints of senior high school students regarding the new standard educational system. Students real-world experiences resulted in new possibilities and ideas for future research on new normal modes.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research aimed to explain and understand the experiences of the Senior High School students during the new normal in the school year 2020-2021. The study is a qualitative research approach, mainly the phenomenological method of inquiry. This research method is a critical process of direct observation, explaining, assessing, and verifying qualitative data (Levitt, McLeod and Stiles, 2021).

Qualitative research provides readers context and understanding and necessitates researchers' deliberation before and during the research process. Researchers should not simply ignore or avoid their own biases; instead, reflective thinking requires researchers to reflect and clearly define their position and perspectives so that readers can better fully comprehend the filters through which questions were asked and data was gathered and analyzed (Sutton and Austin, 2015).

Phenomenology refers to the study of phenomena. A phenomenological investigation shares the meaning of numerous persons' lived experiences of a concept or reality. On the other hand, a transcendental phenomenological approach entails

the researcher bracketing oneself by acknowledging their experiences with the phenomenon under examination (Lowes and Prowse, 2017).

Furthermore, phenomenology is concerned with how performing on phenomena and things entails specific mindset and exercising attentive awareness of the world's objects as we live. The study argues that philosophical exegesis and argumentation are ineffective tools for understanding and explaining the origins of experiential phenomena. The study illustrates how a phenomenologically inspired attitude and ability to apply phenomenological examples to conduct phenomenology directly on things (Van Manen and Van Manen, 2021).

Participants for the study were selected for they have the experiences that the researcher was investigating, were willing to share their thoughts about their point of view, and could articulate well their experiences. A phenomenology should be conducted with a heterogeneous group of a minimum of 3 to a maximum of 15 individuals (Creswell and Poth, 2016).

The researcher obtained data through personal, in-depth, semi-structured, or unstructured one-on-one interviews. The interviews were typically lengthy, and several interview sessions with each participant. She should be skilled at interviewing because of relying on this single data collection method. The interviews were recorded for analysis.

The primary goal was to determine the experience meant for those who had witnessed the phenomenon. This research design was appropriate for achieving the current research's goal and reaching a specific conclusion about the phenomenon's experiences. (Bengtsson, 2016).

In qualitative research, the goal is to gain access to study participants' ideas and feelings. The role is complex since it entails asking people to discuss topics that may be highly sensitive to them. Reliving prior experiences might be challenging at times when the experiences being explored are still fresh in the participant's thoughts. The researcher's primary responsibility is to protect participants and their data, regardless of how it is gathered (Sutton and Austin, 2015).

As a learning support aide in one of the Integrated Schools in Sarangani, the researcher experienced difficulty reaching her learners because they live far from school. She felt disconnected from learners because they could not even message or ask for help with their modules. It was more complicated when she heard from other students that they were experiencing negative emotional states such as stress, anxiety, and sadness because of the new standard of education. Through this study, she wanted to inform, develop knowledge, support, and guide students with their needs, and help facilitate the learning of other individuals.

The researcher also wants to take a role as an advocate to carry the essence of the Senior High School student's experiences based on the findings, how these findings might be extrapolated, and accommodate theoretical discourse regarding the findings. She believes that readers may take approaches as a reciprocated value of the study while recognizing some invalidities shaped by the observational interpretations of the phenomenon described in this study. In such a way, she may provide the best counterarguments which will be posed against her assertions.

The researcher could be a teacher, advocate, evaluator, biographer, theorist, interpreter, constructivist, relativist, and others. Also, she may take the role of an interpreter, constructivist, and relativist. She recognized and substantiated new meanings drawn from this study as a researcher. Thus, whenever there is a complex process, puzzlement, or problem, she connects them with know things, and this connection should be understandable to readers.

Moreover, the researcher had recognized that interpretations vary concerning unique perspectives and experiences of each other relative to their credibility and utility. As the readers derive their meaning as a unique individual, she was a relativist researcher who should consider that differences exist in every aspect of existence. Thus, she should make ethical choices in accommodating these varying perspectives and interpretations in undertaking processes in the research.

The research participants in this study were the six (6) Senior High School Students from Integrated Public School of Alabel 1 District, Division of Sarangani, who wanted to share their experiences during the new normal. This research investigated the experiences of Senior High School students during this new normal. The researcher examined participants with rich experience of this phenomenon, considering their age, grade level, gender, and the school where they enrolled. Also, she felt their willingness to participate in this study to generate meaningful information for the phenomenological analysis.

In selecting the participants in this study, the researcher employed purposeful sampling. It involved identifying and selecting individuals or groups that were knowledgeable about or experienced with a particular phenomenon of interest. To determine the participants, she set inclusion criteria in the selection process as to the gender, age, grade level, school where they are

enrolled, and experience-rich attributes to provide factual information regarding the purpose of the study (Hays and McKibben, 2021).

The phenomenological technique is one of the most extensively utilized research approaches. Sources and procedures of data collection and analysis can be used in this study. Interviews and observations are the preferred and dominant data collection methods. In pursuing understanding and meaning, the researcher is positioned with participants as partners in discovering and generating knowledge (Harrison, Birks, Franklin and Mills, 2017).

First, the researcher determined if the phenomenological study approach is appropriate to the research problem. A phenomenological study is a quality approach when the inquirer has identifiable experiences with boundaries and seeks to understand the experiences in-depth. Next, she identified the participants through purposeful sampling. The study involved Senior High School students enrolled in the Integrated Public school of Alabel 1 District, Division of Sarangani, and focused on the experiences of various individuals as a subject for this study.

The data collected in this study research was typically extensive, drawing on multiple sources of information, such as interviews, documents, and observations. Through this data collection, a detailed description of the study has emerged. The researcher put detailed aspects history of the study, the chronology of events, and the present activities of the study. After this description, she focused on a few key issues or analyses of themes, not to generalize beyond the study but to understand the study's complexity. One analytic strategy was employed to identify the problems within the study to look for common themes that transcend the study. Notably, the researcher employed the rigors of trustworthiness to establish validity, reliability, and objectivity. It is imperative to constitute credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability of the qualitative research study. In conducting this phenomenological study, the researcher considered and included protocols to secure ethical and social aspects. She connected approval letters from the division office, district office, parents, and the school heads to conduct the study with the terms.

The participants, who were the identified sampling, were sent a letter of invitation to secure consent for the conduct of the study. Data collection behavior commenced when the participants affirmed to participate in the study. The researcher informed the participants of the purpose of the research and asked for consent responses recorded for the analysis and interpretation, held with the utmost confidentiality.

Furthermore, the researcher told the participants that the conduct of the study considered their convenience and that when a need arose, freewill to negotiation was undertaken. Also, she notified the participants that the result of the survey served an academic purpose and that no personal interest against the participants underlay the conduct of the study.

The analysis in the study was undertaken as to the specific aspect of the study. The phenomenological approach was utilized due to the qualitative nature of the problem the study aims to solve. Notably, the phenomenological method was utilized to assess the commonality among the lived experience of participants. Data analysis was detailed in description and consists of the analysis of themes through thematic analysis. Based on the research questions, the data collection methods for this descriptive study are used in various combinations and arrangements (Jamon, Boholano, Cabanes-Jamon and Pardillo, 2021).

Personal reflections, note-taking, and documentary analysis were data collection methods or techniques used in grounded theory. The statistical analyses were performed to build and recommend specific approaches or strategies to improve the subject of this study, which were the experiences of Senior High School students during the transition to the new education. In addition, personal reflection and documentary analysis were used to determine significant insights as a teacher (Kibuku, Ochieng and Wausi, 2021).

Then, the researcher used coding, thematic analysis, and categorization to analyze the data. Coding refers to identifying meaning in the text or other data items, searching and identifying concepts, and finding relationships among them. It is used to analyze qualitative information and systematically gain knowledge and understanding about a person, an interaction, a group, a situation, an organization, or a culture.

Categorization is a type of qualitative data analysis by which the researcher attempts to group patterns observed in the data into meaningful units or categories. This process often creates varieties by joining groups of previously coded data. Hence, the student's journey status, particularly their learning pedagogies, will be described using the given methods (Marker and Fink, 2017).

The research participants in this study were the six (6) Senior High School students enrolled in the Integrated Public School of Alabel 1 District, Division of Sarangani. Two students were selected from Banlibato Integrated School, two from Kibac Integrated School, and two from Pag-Asa Integrated school. In choosing the participant, grade level was proven to be considered. The study included only students from senior high schools and was created as a precondition to the research statement and primary objective. Age and gender were not considered when picking the respondent. Before the research needs, the primary criterion required was that students were enrolled in the Senior High School department and program.

To establish the validity, reliability, and objectivity of the qualitative phenomenological studies, adherence to and application of rigors of trustworthiness are imperative. Thus, the researcher observed and considered credibility, transferability, dependability, and confirmability.

The researcher used data collection methods such as in-depth interviews, document analysis of the journal entry, and observation to establish credibility or internal validity. Also, she had a pre-engagement with the participants before conducting the data collection to develop rapport and pleasing conditions with them. Meanwhile, transferability was addressed through a series of interviews with the same set of questions to verify the external validity of the results as it was inconsistent with the initial findings.

On the other hand, dependability was constituted by specifying in detail the research design and its procedural implementation to assure the reliability of the study. In confirmability, the researcher explained the decisions made on favoring one approach over another, giving details, strength, and weaknesses.

The study considered ethical and social considerations. As part of research rigor and preventing the desire to explore this study, several safeguards were employed, assuring the informants its secrecy and non-disclosure measures, wiping out their fears, and establishing trust and confidence. Ethical principles guided the study: respect for persons, beneficence, justice, consent, and confidentiality (Tolley, Ulin, Mack, Robinson and Succop, 2016).

Respect for individuals necessitates a commitment to ensuring the personal freedom of research respondents and, where autonomy may be decreased, to protect people from exploiting their weaknesses. Attach permission from the Schools Division Superintendents and then the school head of the Senior High School learners for the collection and approvals to gather data.

Informed and voluntary consent ensures that Senior High School learners learn what it means to engage in a specific research study to make an informed, deliberate decision on whether or not to participate. The consent form is one of the most valuable tools for ensuring human rights during the research (Ewell, 2022).

Before the researcher conducted the in-depth interviews, she explained the objectives and purpose of this research study verbally and in writing and made clear that the proceedings would be audio-taped. After getting their approval, she asked them to sign a written consent. The informants were also informed of the findings and results of the study since she believed that they had the right to know because they were the ones involved in the first place and to give them recognition as well.

Beneficence necessitates dedication to minimizing research risks, including psychological and social maximizing research respondents' benefits to reduce the risks of harm to the Senior High School learners. The interviewee's anonymity concerning shared information was maintained. Senior High School learners are protected so that data or information files are not left lying around in notebooks or un-protected computer files (Bloom and Crabtree, 2006; Bricki and Green, 2007; Veale, Deutsch, Devor, Kuper, Motmans, Radix and Amand, 2022).

Confidentiality of the findings and protection of the identities of the informants by using a coding system to hide their true identities are explained to them. Teachers informed that the entire database, such as digital voice recorders, typed transcripts, field notes, and other related materials, would be destroyed upon completion of the analysis (Alquizar, 2018; Surmiak, 2018).

Justice necessitates a commitment to ensuring an equal system of the benefits and risks associated with research. The research plan a method of acknowledging the contributions that participants make to the success of the research process and to reimburse them in various ways for their efforts (Bloom and Crabtree, 2006).

An in-depth interview entails conducting intensive personal interviews with respondents to learn about their perspectives on a specific idea, system, or situation. The researcher ask the participants about their experiences, thoughts, and perceptions. The success of an in-depth interview depends mainly on the personal and professional qualities of the interviewer and researcher (Neuman, 2014).

The researcher must also listen carefully, digest, and comprehend the participants' answers. A researcher and interviewer must have a clear and logical mind and think quickly about the critical points of the Senior High School learners' answers. Each early retired teacher was secured that their experiences and personal accounts would be kept, and no one could access the information they entrusted her during the interview. On this basis, the researcher has distinguished a unique outlook and did not make personal comments on the participants' answers during the interviews (Rafferty, 2015; Park and Kim, 2018).

Furthermore, during the study, the well-being of the senior high school learners were considered, and any possible factors that could affect the participants must be acknowledged and addressed. Further, the researcher should also ensure the validity of the collected data by having a learner who could check the transcript of the interviews.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Research Question No 1. How do senior high school students of integrated public schools describe their experiences during the new normal?

To facilitate the generation of comprehensive discussion for the above research problem, the following questions were asked during the in-depth interviews:

1. What motivates you to enroll with the modality you chose?
2. What challenges did you experience in your modality as SHS student of Integrated School?
3. How do these challenges affect you personally? Why do you say so?
4. How did you address the challenges to improve your performance? Tell me more about it.
5. What are your strategies to learn your lessons during this new normal education? (You can rephrase this) Tell me more about it?
6. How do this learning develop you as a student? Give me details about it.

From the data collected on the experiences of the study participants, three major themes emerged as presented in Table 1. These themes aided in determining which core ideas to report. The emergent themes are described as (1) Challenging (2) Hopeful (3) Opportunity.

Based on the responses of both the in-depth interview informants the following data were gathered:

The study discovered that the Senior High School learners view the new normal as challenging. These can be seen in the case of Fighter A, who mentioned that learning was complicated. Fighter B was too many activities given, and Fighter C found it hard to return the module because his home was far from the school. Fighter D experienced learning confusion, Fighter E's lessons were not discussed, and he experienced poor internet connection. Meanwhile, Fighter F struggled with the lesson without guidance and encountered many problems that led to difficulty learning.

The sudden shift of the classes into the new normal has resulted in a more challenging situation, especially for learners without access to technology and even learning difficulties in different subject areas. It can be challenging on an online learning modality and distance learning, and other learning modalities. Due to access and internet connectivity issues, teachers and students have difficulty maintaining academic engagement (Dayagbil, Palompon, Garcia and Olvido, 2021).

The study also revealed that the Senior High School learners view the new normal as optimistic. These could be seen in the case of Fighter A who mentioned that one should be strong to handle the situation, be determined to answer the module, and do everything to learn. Fighter B was vital to face reality and accept the reality presented, and the new normal was a good thing to explore, and Fighter C continues to be motivated and always gave his best in every task given. Fighter D thought positively by not stopping until reaching the goal, and Fighter E enjoyed the situation, promote or has a good mindset, and is motivated. Meanwhile, Fighter F insisted that in this new normal, one should continue dreaming and not lose hope.

Finally, the Senior High School learners viewed the new normal as an opportunity. This could be seen in the case of Fighter B. It was an opportunity for her to develop her skills in note-taking. For Fighter C it was an opportunity for him to be developed, most importantly, to have the motivation and eagerness to learn, and Fighter D it was a time for him to become independent in learning and also an opportunity to have a good answer because of the limitless time given. Meanwhile, Fighter F it was an opportunity for him to be motivated and inspired in learning to gain more knowledge needed.

The COVID-19 pandemic has fundamentally impacted industries worldwide, especially the education sector. Pandemic brought many changes that were hard to cope. However, it also revealed many opportunities in the education sector amidst the difficulties and unpredictable changes to a destination far outside their comfort zone. One of its good sides is the ability to adapt for teachers and learners worldwide (Jespersen, Morris, Hubbs-Tait and Washburn, 2021).

Although directing the impact of COVID-19 is critical, positive technologies can be extremely useful in reducing the psychological impact of the pandemic and assisting individuals in taking root during challenging times. The new normal brought an opportunity among learners; one of these is the utilization of technology and its impact on learning instead of using it for pleasure and other gaming activities. It is an opportunity to discover aid to the new normal in an educational setting (Brenda, Giuseppe and Fabrizia, 2020).

Research Question No. 2: How do senior high school students feel about their experiences during the new normal?

The following questions were asked during the in-depth to find out what senior high school students feel during during new normal.

1. How do you feel when you are about to start your day and learn from home during new normal? Can you tell me more why you feel that way?
2. What do you feel when you are doing school activities and assignments at home? Why do you say so? Tell me in detail.
3. What were the emotions that develop while studying from home during a pandemic? Tell me in details.
4. How do these emotions affect you in learning from home? Why do you say so?
5. To what extent these feelings hinder your productivity? Tell me something about it.
6. What will be the factors that will motivate you to think positively in learning from home during the pandemic? Can you give the reason for it?
7. What will be the factors that will change your mood negatively in learning from home? Why do you say so?
8. What do you feel when problems occur in learning from home? Can you tell me more about it?

Based on the responses of both the in-depth interview informants the following data were gathered:

The Senior High School learners felt some positive emotions during the new normal. These were evident when Fighter A felt happy when she knew the answer to a module. Fighter B mentioned that learning in the new normal was exciting and fun, and Fighter C felt the positivity in doing things freely, like more time to read, having more teachers who guided him at home, and could get up late. Meanwhile, Fighter E felt thankful despite the current situation she experienced.

During the pandemic, some positive effects such as learners having more quality time at home where they can get enough sleep, making meals, improving diet quality, interaction with family members, and fewer academic tasks (Gramigna, 2020; Pradhan, Subedi, Khatiwada, Joshi, Kafle, Chhetri and Bhuj, 2021).

The Senior High School learners felt some negative emotions during the new normal. These were evident in the case of Fighter A felt no excitement in learning, laziness, was dumb and felt afraid not to pass the subject. Fighter C could not focus on learning at home due to the conflict between doing house chores and school matters, and Fighter D lost his interest in learning, which resulted in being unproductive most of the time. Fighter E felt panicked and upset thinking of the module submission deadlines. Meanwhile, Fighter F felt sad when he did not know the answer to the module activity, feeling bored, sad, and asleep.

COVID-19 has taken an international toll on students' mental well-being with consequences. These undesirable circumstances, combined with health-related fears and uncertainty about the future, have brought a wave of negative feelings, including frustration, boredom, tiredness, anxiety, stress, depression, and anger, to students of all academic levels across the world (Camacho-Zuñiga, Pego, Escamilla and Hosseini, 2021).

The Senior High School learners also felt mixed emotions. These were evident in the case of Fighter A and fighter B; they felt like giving up sometimes and feeling happy, sad, and mad. Fighter C felt not pressured, not really excited sometimes, and was bored and could not focus sometimes, and Fighter D lost his interest sometimes. Fighter E felt lazy, a bit worried, and bad sometimes; meanwhile, Fighter F cried and felt so stressed sometimes.

The new normal brought by the pandemic had both positive and negative effects and mixed effects on students' emotions. Students are undergoing a period of rapid physical and mental development, forming their perspectives on life and the world. Emotions exhibit transitional characteristics, such as being quickly excited and unstable. When confronted with an event such as COVID-19, their emotions are bound to be affected (Wang, Jing, Han, Jing and Xu, 2020).

Inevitably, the COVID-19 pandemic has imposed a tremendous emotional burden on learners at all academic levels and threatened their mental health. Universities worldwide face unexpected challenges as learners manifest symptoms of anxiety and stress. While a certain degree of anxiety could be a rational response to uncertainties that revolve around a pandemic experience, different reports highlighted a sharp peak in the prevalence of depressive and anxious symptomatology among students that ranges from moderate to severe (Gavin, Lyne and McNicholas, 2020; Williams, Armitage, Tampe and Dienes, 2020).

From the data collected on the insights of the study participants, three major themes emerged as presented in Table 2. These themes aided in determining which core ideas to report. The emergent themes are described as (1) Positive Emotions (2) Negative Emotions (3) Mixed-emotions.

Research Question No. 3: How does new normal impact their learning experiences of senior high school students?

The following questions were asked during the in-depth to find out the impact on learning experiences of senior high school students during new normal:

1. What do you think is/are the effect of studying from home during new normal as a student of Integrated Public School? Why do you say so?
2. Aside from the effect that you have mentioned, are there any other circumstances that you experience of studying from home during the COVID-19 pandemic? Can you tell me about it?
3. How could these experiences affect you as a student or as a person? Can you elaborate both?
4. What do you think is/are the positive effect of studying from home?
5. What do you think is/are the negative effect of new normal education?
6. How do you cope up with the negative effects in studying from home?
7. What reflection can you share to other senior high school students based from the experiences of studying from home during the new normal?

From the data collected on the insights of the study participants, two major themes emerged as presented in Table 3. These themes aided in determining which core ideas to report. The emergent themes are described as (1) Positive Impact on Time Freedom and Independency and (2) Negative Impact on Learning and Behavior

The study found out that the new normal had a positive effect on the Senior High School learners. These were evident in the case of Fighter A. That new normal made her strong, knowledgeable, and independent, and through this, she could be an inspiration to others. For Fighter B it helped her have more time to answer the module activities to help her parents, and Fighter C said that learning from home was helpful and he could help his parents sell vegetables. Fighter D and E mentioned that they could have more time to answer the module and more time with the family while staying home. Meanwhile, Fighter F said that the new normal and being alone has helped him build up his confidence.

Students across the world have lost the school-going experience. However, it may not be all bad. For instance, the new normal gives some opportunities like the rise of the new approach to learning and technologies for the students and teachers to venture. Even so, every cloud has a positive aspect. Thus, COVID-19 has a positive influence on education as well. For instance, teaching and learning need not be compartmentalized and restrictive. The pandemic has presented the opportunity for collaboration between students and teachers regardless of geography and socio-economic background (Prakriti, 2021; Sapkota, 2021).

The study found that the new normal also harmed the Senior High School learners. These were evident in the case of Fighter A that learning in the new normal is hard, especially in answering the modules, and he might fail in the subject. Fighter B found it hard to answer the activity in the module, was tempted to play online games, and spent the whole time on social media, and Fighter C was not productive, less motivated, and tempted with many distractions. For Fighter D it has affected

her mental and emotional state, while Fighter E became sad and worried the whole day when she did not know the answer to the module and became lazy. Meanwhile, Fighter F insisted that the new normal or the pandemic has no positive effects.

The pandemic has widened its effects on the students. Some students were likely to drop out of school, especially those from low-income families, due to difficulty learning alone and without proper guidance from teachers and parents regarding academic matters. Furthermore, the crisis impacted students' overall health and well-being, with more than 35% of parents being very or enormously worried about their children's mental health (Dorn, Hancock and Sarakatsannis, 2021).

4. DISCUSSION

This part presents the discussion of findings, comparisons of findings to other existing literature, the overall significance of the study, implications for practice, and concluding remarks.

Learners' Views on Learning During the New Normal

It was revealed that the views of the Senior High School during the new normal emerged three emergent themes: challenging, optimistic, and opportunity.

Challenging. The pandemic has disrupted education, affecting over 1.5 billion students. With this, the government had to temporarily close all schools across the country, cease face-to-face instruction, and strictly observe physical distancing. Schools adopted relevant technologies, prepared learning and staff resources, set systems and infrastructure, established new teaching protocols, and adjusted curricula.

With the closure of the school, learners were greatly affected. Generally, most Senior High schools encountered problems in learning, for instance, learning without the presence of the teachers, internet problems, and difficulty in answering the activities in the module due to the limited learning resources and access.

As cited by Dani Dangle and Sumaoan, 2020; Penamora (2021), Self-studying, poor internet connection, lack of sleep, and time to answer all modules due to activities, distractions, and lack of focus were the main challenges that the students have encountered. One of the topics that arose in implementing Modular Distance Learning was the activities in each module. In the learning environment, most of the learners experienced learning difficulties in the new educational setting; difficulty in answering the learning activities in the module, understanding the content, workload, home environment, learning modalities, and struggling with the learning motivation.

According to Canonizado and Penaroma (2021), factors contribute to the difficulty they face. Apart from the learning difficulty, there were problems in terms of family status and issues that could affect learning. As a result, these learners do not perform the required weekly activities. One of the essential topics that arose during the Modular Distance Learning was activities in each module. The Department of Education should consider this issue, reduce activities, and eliminate unnecessary topics to achieve maximum mastery.

According to some of the parents, the less, the better. One of the students' concerns is that they will not have enough time to complete all of the modules in a week. According to Nardo (2017) and De Claro (2021), modules promote independent learning. One advantage of using modules for instruction is that students develop better self-study or learning skills. Students actively participate in understanding the concepts offered up in the module. They gain a sense of responsibility as they complete the module's tasks. The students progress on their own with little or no assistance from others. They are empowered as they learn how to learn.

In the context of the study of Agayon, Agayon and Pentang (2022), the learners find it hard to learn in the new normal. Modular learning is good when the learners comprehend what is being written in the module. Otherwise, if they are struggling to comprehend the text, it will become frustrating on their part.

Rutzler (2020); Oguntade (2021) said that learners could not understand what they read without proper comprehension skills. The point of reading is not to make sounds in the brain to understand essential lessons, stories, and arguments, because having excellent reading comprehension is decisive. It grows the happiness and effectiveness of reading and helps academically, professionally, and in a person's personal life.

However, Dianito, Espinosa, Duran and Tus (2021) said that despite the challenging views of the Senior High School learners towards the new normal, they can still find it to be optimistic during the hard times. Most of them continue learning despite the difficulties encountered. Learners should hold on to their dreams that everything will be back to normal one day.

Fryling-Resare, (2020) cited that the COVID-19 pandemic current events and natural disasters have permeated our lives in the past two years in recent history. People feel overwhelmed and helpless, but shifting to a more positive outlook can help get them through these times.

Hopeful. Most Senior High School learners were very positive despite what they were going through. This kind of attitude is good. However, it would be more achieved when there is parental support; This was crucial in the upbringing of students during the COVID-19 pandemic. They served as learning facilitators and are responsible for controlling their children's development. Typically, they provided information and supported their children in order for them to understand the content of the lessons. They go so far as to clarify and include additional examples that their children comprehend the information. However, not all parents wanted to help their children with their studies.

Opportunity. It was an opportunity to develop their eagerness to learn, be independent in learning, and gain more knowledge they needed to pass their subjects. However, Ariebowo (2021), Deslandes-Martineau, Charland, Arvisais and Vinuesa (2020) said that the pandemic's impact on distance education highlighted the issue of student's independent learning. While students are accustomed to being supervised, guided, and strictly scheduled schoolwork and using resources, including technological tools, school closures have forced them to become more independent in their learning, particularly with parents who are less available to assist them.

In this regard, Reimers, Schleicher, Saavedra and Tuominen's (2020) work plans for increasing student independence and responsibility could be helpful if they are tailored to each student and subject, and students are thoroughly explained how to use them.

Furthermore, work plans as an educational tool could benefit student learning under ordinary situations by encouraging students to take on new challenges and exercise self-discipline, as well as by giving them some control over the methods and tools used to complete tasks.

In the study of Sadeghi (2019), Lee (2021), Labrie, Mok, Tang, Lui, Oehlberg and Poretski (2022), while the learners work independently, it is an opportunity for them to explore a higher level of utilizing technology in learning. Methods of interconnection between learners and teachers need new approaches as classes cannot be simplified in a videoconference or digital setup the same way they have been in a physical, in-person format. Faculty who have adopted technology as a support system for student engagement will likely succeed in this "new normal."

Mostly, teachers have responded to this call, showing an interest in learning and experimenting with new technology that has a long-term impact. Connecting with students through online activities, co-creative discussions, interactive polling, and screencasts has been critical for sustained engagement during this uncertain time.

Moreover, Kim and Asbury (2020); Anzaldo (2021) cited that in the new normal, the learners have more freedom in terms of time; learners have more time to sleep, playtime, and go downtown. However, they should have self-discipline because they spend less time learning activities on their own before the pandemic; only 38% now devote as much or more time to all learning activities.

More study hours mean more positive interactions for some students; for others, it means trying very hard with course materials and needing extra time to catch up. When learners find their activities, they would probably prefer doing other things rather than prioritizing their academic activities. With this, parents play a significant role in motivating and guiding their children.

Senior High School Learners Feel in Learning During the New Normal

It was revealed that the Senior High School students learners emerged with positive, negative, and mixed emotions during the new normal. Emotions being happy and thankful despite the negative situations, fun, and being on the schedule of answering modules.

Positive Emotions. Learners feel positive and negative emotions. Positive emotions included pleasant or desirable situational responses, ranging from interest and contentment to love and joy, but were distinct from pleasurable sensation and undifferentiated positive affect. These emotions are markers of people's overall well-being or happiness and enhance future growth and success. This emotion has been demonstrated in work, school, relationships, mental and physical health, and longevity.

Therefore, Ahrens, Neumann, Kollman, Plichta, Lieb and Tusher (2021) show that positive emotions can help people cultivate a resilient mindset; however, the reality created by the global crisis limits the opportunities for experiencing positive emotions. Thus, it is unclear how long their effect is strong enough to counter the psychological impact of the current pandemic. However, positive emotions are essential to the mental health of high stress, reflected by increased levels of negative emotional experiences.

Negative Emotions. Negative emotions have often been lumped together, regardless of their specific nature, including anger, fear, anxiety, and sadness. Research suggests that different negative emotions have a different impact on cognition and behavior. Other negative emotions for example boredom, burnout, and anxiety are known to diminish cognitive resources, thus negatively impacting school performance and academic achievement.

Thus, Gavin, Lyne and McNicholas (2020); Grubic, Badovinac and Johri (2020) said that learning is the new normal; one should be thinking positively to maintain healthy mental health. Learners maintained being positive despite the problems encountered, especially on academic matters. For this reason, the COVID-19 pandemic has imposed a tremendous emotional burden on learners' at all academic levels and threatened their mental health.

Based on Auerbach, Alonso, Axinn, Cuijpers, Ebert, Green and Mortier (2016), the American College Health Association and World Health Organization (WHO) reported that heightened psychological distress and mental disorders associated with attrition are common among college students temporarily away from their schools. Therefore, the time of lockdown, the result of a global pandemic, is expected to bring alarming consequences at individual and collective levels.

Mixed-Emotions. Most senior high school learners felt affected by negative and positive emotions brought by the new normal called mixed emotion, when they struggled with both implications of what they had experienced. Moreover, colleges, high school, and even elementary were not exempted from the new normal challenges brought by the pandemic. Apart from the physical health complications of the COVID-19 pandemic, the pandemic has also imposed mental, emotional, and social challenges on our lives. Everyone must build awareness around students' feelings, empower them to regulate their feelings effectively, and seek help and support during this biological disaster.

Thus, according to Buheji and Sisk (2020); Dozois (2021), daily routines have been disrupted, many people have been separated from loved ones, and anxiety levels have reached an all-time high. Everyone reacts differently to difficult or stressful situations. While being concerned is natural and intended in this new normal, it is easy to fall into panic or feel completely overwhelmed. Many uncomfortable emotions can arise if one does not care about protecting emotions, such as sadness, anger, frustration, and hopelessness.

Dalal, Roy, Choudhary, Kar and Tripathi (2020) believed that unaddressed emotional concerns could lead to negative consequences such as changes in rest hours and diet, difficulty concentrating, physical illnesses, strained relationships, and even thoughts of suicide. Especially for learners during this time of uncertainty, emotional well-being to think clearly and maintain good thinking in pursuing their studies.

Effects/ Impact of the New Normal Among the Learners

Finally, according to Raharjo, Hendartho, Susanti and Ekasari (2021), the effects or impact of the new normal among the Senior High School learners revealed two emergent themes: positive and negative effects. These findings showed that there was always a good thing about it. It depended on the person to handle it, especially the new normal brought about by the pandemic.

Positive Impact on Time Freedom and Independence.

People perceived positive and negative effects on their lives. Lockdown and staying home strategies have been put in place as the needed action to flatten the curve and control the transmission of the disease; these give more people a brief time to reflect and have more time with the family. However, it affected their work, which resulted in income loss.

Similarly, based on Dumalagan, Mella and Esquita (2021), learners worldwide experienced problems in their learning due to the new normal restrictions. Learners just stay and study at home with the chosen learning modalities; it can be offline through modular distance learning or online learning. However, despite these alternative ways, learners still encounter different issues in learning. For instance, Senior High School learners find both positive and negative experiences.

Sintema (2020); Pokhrel and Chhetri (2021) cited that the new normal impacted the academic performance of the learners that drop classes held for both year-end examination and internal examination due to reduced contact hours and lack of consultation with teachers facing difficulties in learning. Moreover, they also find it hard to comprehend the lesson content, the learning modality they have chosen, getting and returning to school module, home problems and conflict between class schedule and house chores, finances, and others.

According to Quinn (2011); Rawat, Kumari and Saha (2021), the education system and the educators have adopted "Education in Emergency" through various learning platforms and are compelled to adopt a system that they are not prepared. Educators, and learners face frequent hiccups while using or referring to these tools in a sea of platforms and online educational tools.

However, according to Jowsey, Foster, Cooper-Ioelu and Jacobs (2020), there is an adjustment in online learning of teachers and learners to adopt new learning styles on active learning and technical support for delivery of teaching. In the new normal, universities worldwide have transitioned to distance education, most of which is planned for online delivery. Health professional courses may use various tools like synchronous online tutorials, E-learning in simulation sessions, asynchronous activity in moderated discussion forums, formative quizzes, and other teacher-directed or self-directed learning activities. Engaging with these learning methods may be perceived differently from conventional classroom-based teaching.

Negative Impact on Learning and Behavior

The new normal is not only about the opposing sides but also it impacted or has positive effects. Analyzing the present days, one can clearly outline that some of the touched parts by the COVID-19 can be somehow improved or redefined in the right direction. When discussing the positive impact of a pandemic, one thing that comes into mind is the integration of technologies into the education system.

According to Gelles, Lord, Hoople, Chen and Mejia, 2020; Anzaldo (2021), in the new normal, the learners have more freedom in terms of time; learners have more time to sleep, playtime, and go downtown. However, they should have self-discipline because learners have less time on learning activities before the pandemic; only 38 percent now spend more time on all learning activities. For some students, more study hours mean more positive engagement; for others, it means struggling with course materials and needing additional time to catch up. When learners find their activities, they would probably prefer doing other things rather than prioritizing their academic activities. With this, parents play a significant role in motivating and guiding their children.

Moreover, Budimirovic and Filipova (2020) said that education and technologies always come together, but with the pandemic, it took a new level. However, new technology in education does not mean that it will improve the interaction between teacher and student, meaning that the teacher will deliver material better and students will receive it and fully understand it.

As cited by Martin and Bolliger (2018); Putra, Liriwati, Tahrim, Syafrudin and Aslan (2020), technology is a part of students' lives. Incorporating technology into the classroom has proven beneficial while having some drawbacks. Technology has increased student willingness and engagement while also allowing for improved learning. Because of the need for construction and engagement, the best types of learning will involve choices that the student can make and learn in contexts where the student is engaged.

According to Gilbert, Montefiori, McDermott, Fong, Benkeser and Deng (2022), one of the effects of the global crisis on education is the disruption of instruction and teaching methods. According to the government's assertion, no one expected this faceless enemy to drag the educational system, resulting in the driving ban of classes and the cancellation of scheduled activities.

Ratten (2020); Lee and Ates (2021) cited that there is no doubt that the pandemic caused incredible upheaval in higher education, but the positive impacts of that disruption are significant. COVID-19 has proven to be a direct catalyst for what was almost certainly an inevitable shift toward the increased attractiveness of remote learning. As educators adjust their approaches and students hone valuable skills, the sector prepares for new education and benefits from its inspired innovation. As challenges remain on the horizon, such as tackling issues of accessibility and equity in a technology-dependent future, professionals at every level can address these challenges with clearer vision, greater confidence, and increased support from both within and outside the industry.

Implications for Practice

Based on the experiences of the six informants of this study, the researcher sought to seek the realities of understanding the experiences of the Senior High School in the new normal. The researcher believed that this undertaking would be a significant source of information not only for the locale of the study but also for all the learners who undertake the same experiences in the new normal.

On the learner's view in learning during the new normal

Challenging. Learners may likely experience worry, anxiety, and fear, but learners must accept reality and can work to change and improve learning. However, learning from home, learning online to stay engaged for some time in class, and talking with peers and teachers is challenging. Remember to reflect on knowledge in learning online or in modular. As Saline (2021) stated, adults must promote a sense of security, appropriate reassurance, essential information, stress reduction tools, and healthy lifestyle choices related to sleep, eating, and exercise.

Hopeful. Learners may think positively as always and continue to strive for their dreams. They may stay strong to handle the situation and continue being motivated to promote growth and mindset. Learners must be determined to study online or modular and continue to go on their dreams.

Opportunity. New education may be challenging but be a goal-driven student, always think that it is an opportunity to strive harder and encourage that even though it is a pandemic, learners still have the chance to achieve their dreams.

On learners' feeling in learning during the new normal

Positive Emotions. A pandemic may result in positive impacts; for instance, learners may have quality time at home where they can have enough sleep. As Gramigna (2020) asserted, increasing the amount of time spent at home, the amount of time spent making meals, the quality of one's nutrition, the amount of time spent interacting with family members, and decreasing academic responsibilities could increase good emotions during difficult times.

Negative Emotions. The learners may take control of these emotions by communicating with peers, teachers, and especially with the family. Learners may do activities like taking a walk early in the morning, making healthy foods, and learning materials at home. According to Camacho-Zuniga (2021), undesirable circumstances combined with health-related fears and uncertainty about the future have brought negative feelings, including frustration, boredom, tiredness, anxiety, stress, depression, and anger.

Mixed Emotions. The new normal may bring both positive and negative effects and mixed effects on students. Students are undergoing a phase of rapid intellectual development, during which their perspectives on life and the world eventually take shape. Students may learn to notice and identify that feelings take practice. In addition to focusing on feelings, check the body and feelings as Wang (2020) said that the transition period's characteristics are excitement and instability. Faced with events such as COVID-19, their emotions will inevitably be affected.

On effects/impact on the new normal among the SHSs learners

Positive impact on Time, Freedom, and Independence. Students across the world have lost the school-going experience. However, it may not be all bad. For instance, the new normal gives opportunities for learners like the rise of the new approach to learning and technologies for the students and teachers to venture.

Thus, COVID-19 has a positive strike on education as well. For instance, teaching and learning do not need to be compartmentalized and restrictive, as Prakriti (2021) affirmed that the pandemic had presented the opportunity for collaboration between students and teachers regardless of geography, socio-economic background, or any other factors.

Negative impact on learning and behavior. The pandemic may widen its effects on the students. Students wanted to drop out of school from low-income families due to difficulty learning and without proper guidance from teachers and parents regarding academic matters. Further, according to Dorn (2021), the crisis impacted the broader health and well-being of students, with more than 35 percent of parents very concerned about their children's mental health.

Based on the study, it is recommended that the Department of Education (DepEd) should have a comprehensive program on mental health. It should be based on every learning modality implemented. It is because; learners having modular instruction might have different needs in terms of mental and emotional problems from the learners who attended online learning. The crafted program should be handed down to every school for the direct and easy implementation of the program.

This program can save learners suffering from negative and mixed emotions (Rotas and Cahapay, 2020; Arrieta and Valeria, 2021).

On the other hand, the new normal is not only about the opposing sides but also impacted or has positive effects. Analyzing the present days, one can clearly outline that some of the touched parts by the COVID-19 can be somehow improved or redefined in the right direction. The positive impact of a pandemic is the integration of technologies into the education system (Magomedov, Khaliev and Khubolov, 2020).

Before taking steps to guarantee that learners are physically, emotionally, and psychologically prepared, it is advised that the Department of Education assess the students. There should be an intervention done in all schools like debriefing on the mental health for the learners to understand the situation and have better behavior or responses to the current situations (Kim, Lee, Chung, Yoon, Shin, Choi and Nam, 2021).

Finally, based on the revealed experiences of the six informants, the study's conclusions or findings were unable to make any generalizations for other concerned and relevant individuals. As a result, the researcher recommends that research relevant to this study be conducted at other research sites and with other carefully chosen people to confirm and compare the significant findings.

Overall Significance

Senior High School students from various grade levels and integrated public schools benefit from and the drawbacks of the new learning despite the ongoing pandemic throughout the country. This study has taught us to appreciate the students' unique viewpoints on their diverse environments and socio-economic condition. They discussed their pleasant and unhappy experiences to provide us with the findings to complete this research report. Despite the new educational system's negative consequences on students, each response demonstrated their commitment to complete the school year by utilizing their incentive to work harder.

Thus, this research aims to make available to the general public the experiences and viewpoints of senior high school students regarding the new standard educational system. Students real-world experiences resulted in new possibilities and ideas for future research on new normal modes.

Concluding Remarks

The result of this study served to be an insight into the experiences of the Senior High School in the new normal. The study found that the learners view the new normal as challenging, optimistic, and an opportunity. As to the feelings, the learners found the new normal creates negative, positive, and mix-emotions which is the combination of positive and negative emotions. Meanwhile, the Senior High School experienced the positive and negative effects of the new normal in the education setting (Shen, Dillard and Peng, 2022).

The current COVID-19 pandemic has added unusual challenges to the education systems, and no one knows when it will end. Every country is implementing plans and strategies to contain the virus, but infections are still on. In order to maintain a quality education despite crowd control and community quarantine, the suggested educational policy must incorporate the new norm (Oberoi, Halsall and Snowden, 2021).

The researcher believes that the pandemic will not only have possible long-lasting effects on the educational system, but its lessons will also lead to a more fundamental change. Resilience amidst the threat to health requires all of us to act differently. As the nation tackles the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Education has increased its use of responsive, timely, and relevant learning modalities. It is keen to explore new pathways to avoid impeding the educational process (Peimani and Kamalipour, 2021).

While exploring different alternatives, the Department of Education may find ways not only to uplift the quality of education among its stakeholders should also to embark on comprehensive programs for the impact of the new normal on the health of the learners in general. Apart from the physical health complications of the COVID-19 pandemic, the pandemic has also imposed mental, emotional, and social challenges on our lives. Understanding the emotional state of feelings of the individual builds awareness around students' feelings and empowers them to effectively regulate their feelings and seek help and support during this biological disaster (Camacho-Zuñiga, Pego, Escamilla and Hosseini, 2021).

In conclusion, with every school's new normal, it is necessary to address problems, plans, and procedures. In the midst of challenging times, collaboration is the most vital factor to consider. We should contribute to the formation of post-COVID-

19 education, embracing the new standard. The challenge herewith is how to provide and deliver quality education amidst exceptional times, like the COVID-19 pandemic, and become more prepared when another crisis comes in the future (Joshi and Gupta, 2021).

REFERENCES

- [1] Abrigo, C., & Torres, E. (2022). Face-to-face with the new normal: libraries' readiness and perspectives toward the changing service environment. *Library Management*, 22-25.
- [2] Agayon, A. J. D., Agayon, A. K. R., & Pentang, J.T. (2022). Teachers in the new normal: Challenges and coping mechanisms in secondary schools. *International Journal of Humanities and Education Development (IJHED)*, 4 (1), 67-75.
- [3] Ahrens K. F., Neumann R. J., Kollman B., Plichta M.M., Lieb K., Tusher O., et al. (2021). Differential Impact of COVID- related lockdown on mental health in Germany. *World Psychiatry* 20, 140-141. 10.1002/wps.20830, PMID:- PMC PubMed.
- [4] Akpınar, E. (2021). The Effect of Online Learning on Tertiary Level Students Mental Health during the COVID-19 Lockdown. *The European Journal of Social & Behavioral Sciences*, 86-90.
- [5] Alazzam, M., Abuhammad, S., Twalbeh, L., Dalky, H. (2020). Prevalence and correlates of depression, anxiety and suicidality among high school students: A national study. *Journal of Psuchosocial Nursing and Mental Health Services*, 23(2), 23-28.
- [6] Albor, B. S., Gatchalian-Fortes, A. C., & Delumen-Albor, M. R. I. (2020) Distance Learning Landscape in Bulan Districts.
- [7] Aldevera, A. (2019) Lived Experiences of the Senior High School Teachers. Can-asujan National High School. *Educational Journal*, 56-70.
- [8] Alexander, R., Aragon, O. R., Bookwala, J., Cherbuin, N., Gatt, J. M., Kahrilas, I. J., & Styliadis, C. (2021). The neuroscience of positive emotions and effect: Implications for cultivating happiness and wellbeing. *Neuroscience & Biobehavioral Reviews*, 121, 220-249.
- [9] Ali, W. (2020). Online and remote learning in higher education institutes: A necessity in light of COVID-19 pandemic. *Higher education studies*, 10(3), 16-25.
- [10] Aliyu, U. I., Muhammad, U. I., Auta, M. A., & Muhammed, A. K. (2021). Exploring Students' Experience on Distance Education During the COVID-19 Pandemic in Bauchi State Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Assessment in Teaching and Learning*, 11(2), 93-102.
- [11] Almaiah, M. A., Al-Khasawneh, A., Althunibat, A., & Almomani, O. (2021). Exploring the main determinants of mobile learning application usage during Covid-19 pandemic in Jordanian universities. In *Emerging Technologies During the Era of COVID-19 Pandemic* (pp. 275-290). *Springer, Cham*.
- [12] Alquizar, J. (2018). Multitasking of Teachers in the Contemporary Settings: Boon or Bane?. Available at SSRN 3283601.
- [13] Anas, A. L., Salifu, M., & Abdulai, M. (2022). Contemporary Mobility Decisions of International and Danish Students in Denmark Amidst the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Human Arenas*, 1-25.
- [14] Anzaldo, G. (2021). Modular Distance Learning in the New Normal Education Amidst Covid-1. Volume 2. *International Journal of Scientific Advances*. DO 10.51542/ijsciaiv2i3.6
- [15] Ariebowo, T. (2021). Autonomous learning during COVID-19 pandemic: Students' objectives and preferences. *Journal of Foreign Language Teaching and Learning*, 6(1), 56-77.
- [16] Aristovnik, A., Kerzic, D., Ravselj, D., Tomazevic, N., & Umek, L. (2020). Impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic on life of higher education students: A global perspective. *Sustainability*, 12(20), 84-88.

- [17] Arrieta, G. S., & Valeria, J. R. (2021). Counseling Challenges in the New Normal: Inputs for Quality Guidance and Counseling Program. *Counsellia: Journal Bimbingan dan Konseling*, 11(1), 71-85.
- [18] Artino, A. R., & Stephens, J. M. (2009). Beyond grades in online learning: adaptive profiles of academic self-regulation among naval academy undergraduates. *Journal of Advanced Academics*, 20 (4), 568-601.
- [19] Ates, O. (2021). During Times of Disruption: The Experience of Emergency Remote Teaching in Higher Education in Turkey. In *Handbook of Research on Lessons Learned from Transitioning to Virtual Classrooms During a Pandemic* (pp. 292-312). *IGI Global*.
- [20] Auerbach, R. P., Alonso, JW., Axinn, G., Cuijpers, P., Ebert, D.D., Green, J.G., Mortier., V (2016). Mental disorders among College students in the World Health Organization world mental health surveys *psycho. Med.*, 46 (14), pp. 255-297.
- [21] Baltà-Salvador, R., Olmedo-Torre, N., Peña, M., & Renta-Davids, A. I. (2021). Academic and emotional effects of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic on engineering students. *Education and information technologies*, 26(6), 7407-7434.
- [22] Bayod, R., & Bayod, C. (2020). Laying the groundworks for education of children in the new normal: The case of Deped Southern Mindanao. *Eubios Journal of Asian and International Bioethics* 30 (8), 443-449.
- [23] Beck, M. J., & Hensher, D. A. (2020). Insights into the impact of COVID-19 on household travel and activities in Australia—The early days under restrictions. *Transport policy*, 96, 76-93.
- [24] Bengtsson, M. (2016). How to plan and perform a qualitative study using content analysis. *NursingPlus open*, 2, 8-14.
- [25] Blanco, Q. A., Carlota, M. L., Nasibog, A. J., Rodriguez, B., Saldana, X. V., Vasquez, E. C., & Gagani, F. (2020). Probing on the Relationship between students' Self-Confidence and Self-Efficacy while engaging in Online Learning Amidst COVID-19. *Journal La Edusci*, 1(4), 16-25.
- [26] Blair, L. (2021). Responding To Campus Bias and Hate: A Proactive Way to Protect Marginalized Students from Race-Based Trauma, 78-85.
- [27] Bloem, B. R., Dorsey, E. R., & Okun, M. S. (2020). The coronavirus disease 2019 crisis as catalyst for telemedicine for chronic neurological disorders. *JAMA neurology*, 77(8), 927-928.
- [28] Brooks, C., Gierdowski, C. (2021). Student Experiences with Technology in the Pandemic. *Educause Research*. <https://library.educause.edu/resources/2021/4/student-experiences-with-technology-in-the-pandemic>.
- [29] Bricki, N., & Green, J. (2007). A guide to using qualitative research methodology. *Journal La Edusci*, 1(5), 20-21.
- [30] Brown, C. M., Vostok, J., Johnson, H., Burns, M., Gharpure, R., Sami, S., ... & Laney, A. S. (2021). Outbreak of SARS-CoV-2 infections, including COVID-19 vaccine breakthrough infections, associated with large public gatherings—Barnstable County, Massachusetts, July 2021. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 70(31), 1059.
- [31] Budimirovic, M., Filipova, V. (2020). *Technology in times of pandemic*. <https://mag.wcoomd.org/magazine/wco-news-94/technology-in-times-of-pandemic/>.
- [32] Buheji, M., & Sisk, F. C. W. (2020). You and the new normal: Jobs, pandemics, relationship, climate change, success, poverty, leadership and belief in the emerging new world. *Author House*.
- [33] Buonerba, A., Corpuz, M. V. A., Ballesteros, F., Choo, K. H., Hasan, S. W., Korshin, G. V., & Naddeo, V. (2021). Coronavirus in water media: Analysis, fate, disinfection and epidemiological applications. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 415-580.
- [34] Cahapay, M. B. (2021). The Phenomenon of Leading without Guidebook: Educational Leadership Practices of Philippine School Principals in Virulent COVID-19 Times. *International Journal of Educational Leadership and Management*, 7(9), 235-325.
- [35] Callo, E. C., & Yazon, A. D. (2020). Exploring the factors influencing the readiness of faculty and students on online teaching and learning as an alternative delivery mode for the new normal. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 8(8), 350-358.

- [36] Camacho- Zuniga, C., Pego, L., Escamilla, J., Hosseini, S., (2016). Heliyon Volume7. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S24058440210005703>.<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyonn.2021.e06465>
- [37] Canonizado, I. (2021). Challenges that Teachers are Facing under the New Normal System in Education. *Teachers Are Facing Under the New Normal System in Education*, 5-15.
- [38] Castillo, E. C. (2020) Adjustments on the Awards and Recognition of Learners' Performance this School Year Under the COVID-19 Global Pandemic. *Universal Journal of Educational Research*, 7(8), 34093417.
- [39] Chalkey, A. E., Routen, A. C., Harris, J. P., Cale, L. A., Gorely, T., & Sherar, L. B. (2018). A retrospective qualitative evaluation of barriers and facilitators to the implementation of a school-based running programme. *BMC Public Health*, 18(1), 1-12.
- [40] Chan, Z. C., Fung, Y. L., & Chien, W. T. (2013). Bracketing in phenomenology: Only undertaken in the data collection and analysis process. *The qualitative report*, 18(30), 1-9.
- [41] Cohn, M. A., & Fredrickson, B. L. (2009). Positive emotions *Oxford handbook of positive psychology*, 2, 13-24.
- [42] Cornu, B. (1995). New technologies: integration into education. In *Integrating information technology into education* (pp. 3-11). *Springer, Boston, MA*. 65-80.
- [43] Cortez, C. P. (2020). Blended, distance, electronic and virtual-learning for the new normal of mathematics education: A senior high school students' perception. *European Journal of Interactive Multimedia and Education*, 1(1), e02001.
- [44] Creswell, J. W., & Poth, C. N. (2016). *Qualitative inquiry and research design: Choosing among five approaches*. *Sage publications*, 62-80.
- [45] Dalal, P. K., Roy, D., Choudhary, P., Kar, S. K., & Tripathi, A. (2020). Emerging mental health issues during the COVID-19 pandemic: An Indian perspective. *Indian journal of psychiatry*, 62(Suppl 3), S354.
- [46] Dani Dangle, Y.R. & Sumaoan, J. D. (2020). The Implementation of Modular Distance Learning in the Philippines Secondary Public Schools. <https://www.dpublication.com/wpcontent/uploads/2020/1/27427.pdf>, S.J(200). *EduvationandtheCOVID19pandemic.Prospects*.<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11125-020-09464-3>.
- [47] Daniel, S. J. (2020). Education and the COVID-19 pandemic. *Prospects*, 49(1), 91-96.
- [48] Dayagbil, F., Palompon, D., Garcia, L., Olvido, M.M (2021). Teaching and Learning Continuity Amid and Beyond the Pandemic. *Frontiers education*<https://w.frontiersin.org/article/10.3389/educ.2021.678692>DOI=10.3389/educ.21678692.
- [49] De Claro, W. N. D. (2021). Challenges and Barriers Encountered by G10-Agoncillo Learners in the Implementation of Modular Distance Learning at Taal National High School. *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Management*, 4(7), 409-413.
- [50] Delgado, P. (2019). The Importance of Parental Involvement in Teaching <https://observatory.tec.mx/edunewsthe-importance-of-parental-involvement-in-teaching>, 56(2), 89-94.
- [51] Delima, E. (2018, September). The importance of multimedia learning modules(mlms) based on local wisdom as an instructional media of 21stcenturyphysics learning. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1097, No. 1, p.012018).
- [52] Deslandes-Martineau, M., Charland, P., Arvisais, O., Vinuesa, V. (2020). Education and COVID-19: Challenges and opportunities. <https://en.ccunesco.ca/idealab/education-and-covid19challengesopportunities>
- [53] Dianito, A. J., Espinosa, J., Duran, J., & Tus, J. (2021). A glimpse into the lived experiences and challenges faced of PWD students towards online learning in the Philippines amidst COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Advance Research and Innovative Ideas in Education*, 7(1), 1206-1230.
- [54] Diaz, M. C. G., & Walsh, B. M. (2021). Telesimulation-based education during COVID-19. *The Clinical Teacher*, 18(2), 121-125.
- [55] Dicicco-Bloom, B., & Crabtree, B. F. (2006). The qualitative research interview. *Medical education*, 40(4), 314-321.

- [56] Diliberti, M., Schwartz, H. L., & Grant, D. M. (2021). *Stress topped the reasons why public school teachers quit, even before COVID-19*. RAND.
- [57] Dimaculangan, K. A., Abas, H. H., & Quinto, C. S. (2022). Narrative Study of Teaching Strategies and Challenges Encountered by Teachers in Synchronous Online Classes. *International Journal of Social Learning (IJSL)*, 2(2), 201-216.
- [58] Donnelly, R., & Fitzmaurice, M. (2005). Designing modules for learning. *Emerging issues in the practice of university learning and teaching*, 99-110.
- [59] Dorn, E., Hancock, B., Sarakatsannis, J. (2021). COVID-19 and education: The Lingering effects of unfinished learning. <https://www.mckinsey.com/industries/education/ourinsights/covid19andeducation-the-lingering-effects-of-unfinished-learning>.
- [60] Dozois, D. J. (2021). Anxiety and depression in Canada during the COVID-19 pandemic: A national survey. *Canadian Psychology/psychologie canadienne*, 62(1), 136.
- [61] Dumalagan, A. B., Mella, M. C. G., & Esquita, M. D. S. 2021 Bridging the Digital Divide: Enhancing Academic outcomes of disadvantaged learners in distance education through offline video lessons. *Journal of International Law*, 56(3).
- [62] Dwivedi, Y. K., Hughes, D. L., Coombs, C., Constantiou, I., Duan, Y., Edwards, J. S., ... & Upadhyay, N. (2020). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on information management research and practice: Transforming education, work and life. *International journal of information management*, 55, 102211.
- [63] Espinal Ramos, P. (2022). The Impact of Social Isolation during the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Personal Account of Social Isolation.
- [64] Evans, S., Alkan, E., Bhangoo, J., Tenenbaum, H., Ng-Knight, T. (2021). Effects of the COVID-19 lockdown on mental health, wellbeing, sleep, and alcohol use in a UK student sample, *Psychiatry Research*, Volume 298. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S016178121001165><https://doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2021.113819>.
- [65] Ewell, C. (2022). The Potential for Meaningful and Mandatory Corporate Due Diligence to Ensure Free, Prior and Informed Consent Rights in the Renewable Energy Transition. *Yale Journal of International Law*, 47(2).
- [66] Fisher, A., Exley, K., & Ciobanu, D. (2017). Using technology to support learning and teaching. London: Routledge, Taylor & Francis Group.
- [67] Fontenelle-Tereshchuk, D. (2021). Mental health and the COVID-19 crisis: The hopes and concerns for children as schools re-open. *Interchange*, 52(1), 1-16.
- [68] Fryling-Resare, K. (2020). 10 Ways to Stay Positive during Tough Times: <https://www.nursingcenter.com/ncblog/october-2020/10-ways-to-stay-positive-during-tough-times>.
- [69] Gavin, B., Lyne, J., McNicholas, F. (2020). Mental health and the COVID-19 pandemic. *Ir. J. Psychol. Med.* pp. 1-7
- [70] Gbollie, C., & Keamu, H. P. (2017). Student academic performance: The role of motivation, strategies, and perceived factors hindering Liberian junior and senior high school students learning. *Education Research International*, 2017.
- [71] Gelles, L. A., Lord, S. M., Hoople, G. D., Chen, D. A., & Mejia, J. A. (2020). Compassionate flexibility and self-discipline: Student adaptation to emergency remote teaching in an integrated engineering energy course during COVID-19. *Education Sciences*, 10(11), 304.
- [72] Gholami, M., Fawad, I., Shadan, S., Rowaiee, R., Ghanem, H., Khamis, A. H., & Ho, S. B. (2021). COVID-19 and healthcare workers: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 104, 335-346.

- [73] Gilbert, P. B., Montefiori, D. C., McDermott, A. B., Fong, Y., Benkeser, D., Deng, W., & United States Government (USG)/CoVPN Biostatistics Team §. (2022). Immune correlates analysis of the mRNA-1273 COVID-19 vaccine efficacy clinical trial. *Science*, 375(6576), 43-50.
- [74] Gilbert, P. K. (2022). Responsibility and Community: Narrating the Individual and the Collective in Pandemic Times. *Journal of Victorian Culture*, 56-70.
- [75] Giuseppe, R., Fabrizia, M., and Brenda., K. (2020). Wiederhold.Cyber psychology,Behavior, and Social Networking.581 587. <http://doi.org/10.1089/cyber.2020.29194.gri>
- [76] Gocotano, T. E., Jerodiaz, M. A. L., Banggay, J. C. P., Nasibog, H. B. R., & Go, M. B. (2021). Higher Education Studentsâ€™ Challenges on Flexible Online Learning Implementation in the Rural Areas: A Philippine Case. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 20(7).
- [77] Gramigma, J. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic has both positive and negative effects on youth sleep, quality of life.<https://www.healio.com/news/neurology/20210720/covid19pandemic-has-both-positive-and-negative-effects-on-youth-sleep-quality-of-life>.
- [78] Grubic, N., Badovinac, S., Johri, A.M. (2020). Student mental health in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic: a call for further research and immediate solutions *Int. J. Soc. Psychiatr.*, Article 0020764020925108.
- [79] Hareli, S., & Hess, U. (2008). The role of causal attribution in hurt feelings and related social emotions elicited in reaction to other's feedback about failure. *Cognition and emotion*, 22(5), 862-880.
- [80] Harrison, H., Birks, M., Franklin, R., & Mills, J. (2017, January). Case study research: Foundations and methodological orientations. In *Forum qualitative Sozialforschung/Forum: qualitative social research* (Vol. 18, No. 1, pp. 1-17).
- [81] Hays, D. G., & McKibben, W. B. (2021). Promoting rigorous research: Generalizability and qualitative research. *Journal of Counseling & Development*, 99(2), 178-188.
- [82] Hidayat, D., & Wibawa, D. (2020). Crisis management and communication experience in education during the covid-19 pandemic in Indonesia. *Journal Komunikasi: Malaysian Journal of Communication*, 36(3).
- [83] Ilyasa, F., Rahmayanti, H., Muzani, M., Ichsan, I. Z., & Suhono, S. (2020). Environmental education for prevent disaster: a survey of student's knowledge in beginning new normal of COVID-19. *International Journal on Advanced Science, Education, and Religion*, 3(2), 1-8.
- [84] Inguva, P., Shah, P., Shah, U., & Brechtelsbauer, C. (2021). How to design experiential learning resources for independent learning. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 98(4), 1182-1192.
- [85] Israelashvili, J. (2021). More positive emotions during the COVID-19 pandemic are associated with better resilience, especially for those experiencing more negative emotions. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 12, 1635.
- [86] Jabbar, H., Fong, C. J., Germain, E., Li, D., Sanchez, J., Sun, W. L., & Devall, M. (2022). The competitive effects of school choice on student achievement: A systematic review. *Educational Policy*, 36(2), 247-281.
- [87] Jamon, B. E. V., Boholano, H. B., Cabanes-Jamon, M. G., & Pardillo, M. F. (2021). Teachers lived experiences in the new normal in Philippine public schools: A phenomenology. *International Journal of Research*, 8(02), 773-782.
- [88] Jaspersen, J. E., Morris, A. S., Hubbs-Tait, L., & Washburn, I. J. (2021, October). Evaluation of a Parent Education Program Emphasizing Responsive Parenting and Mindfulness: An Inclusive Randomized Controlled Trial. In *Child & Youth Care Forum* (Vol. 50, No. 5, pp. 859-883). *Springer US*.
- [89] Jimenez, E. (2021). Project New-Normal Navigating Electronic World to Numerous Online Resources of Modality Approaches in Learning *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 2(1), 70-76.
- [90] Jacinto, M. A. P., Molina, K. S. S., Jungco, J. S., Cardaño, A. B., Berbos, J. A., Vargas, A. J. V & Francisco, C. D. Social Media Platform and its Impact on the Academic Performance of Senior High School Students in the New Normal Learning System. *International Journal of Research*, 3(8), 89-91.

- [91] Jamon, B. E. V., Boholano, H. B., Cabanes-Jamon, M. G., & Pardillo, M. F. (2021). Teachers lived experiences in the new normal in Philippine public schools: A phenomenology. *International Journal of Research*, 8(02), 773-782.
- [92] Johar, R. (2020, February). The Development of Trigonometry E-Modules for Senior HighSchool Using Differentiated Instruction (DI) Approach. In *Journal of Physics: Conference Series* (Vol. 1462, No. 1, p. 012017).
- [93] Joshi, V. A., & Gupta, I. (2021). Assessing the impact of the Covid-19 pandemic on hospitality and tourism education in India and preparing for the new normal. *Worldwide Hospitality and Tourism Themes*.
- [94] Joyce, L. (2020). The New Normal: Projecting the Impact Of COVID-19 Education. <https://www.wfdd.org/story/new-normal-projecting-impact-covid-19-education>.
- [95] Jowsey T, Foster G, Cooper-Ioelu P, Jacobs S. (2020) Blended learning via distance in pre- registration nursing education: A scoping review. *Nurse Educ Pract.* 2020;44:102775.
- [96] Khan, A. S., Alnmer, M. S., Khan, S. A., & Khan, M. M. R. (2022). Assessment of the effectiveness of EFL online learning and teaching during Covid-19 pandemic. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 6(2), 2150-2159.
- [97] Kibuku, R. N., Ochieng, D. O., & Wausi, A. N. (2021). Developing an e-Learning Theory for Interaction and Collaboration Using Grounded Theory: A Methodological Approach. *The Qualitative Report*, 26(9), 0_1-2854.
- [98] Kim, J. E., Lee, Y. L., Chung, M. A., Yoon, H. J., Shin, D. E., Choi, J. H., & Nam, E. W. (2021). Effects of social prescribing pilot project for the elderly in rural area of South Korea during COVID-19 pandemic. *Health Science Reports*, 4(3), e320.
- [99] Kim, L. E., & Asbury, K. (2020). 'Like a rug had been pulled from under you': The impact of COVID-19 on teachers in England during the first six weeks of the UK lockdown. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 90(4), 1062-1083.
- [100] King, O. (2021). Two sets of qualitative research reporting guidelines: An analysis of the shortfalls. *Research in Nursing & Health*, 44(4), 715-723.
- [101] Labrie, A., Mok, T., Tang, A., Lui, M., Oehlberg, L., & Poretski, L. (2022). Toward Video-Conferencing Tools for Hands-On Activities in Online Teaching. Proceedings of the ACM on Human-Computer Interaction, *Journal of Education*, 6(GROUP), 1-22.
- [102] Lee, A. (2021). How COVID-19 Created Opportunities for Teachers and Students. <https://campustechnology.com/Articles/2021/05/05/HowCOVID-19-Created-Opportunities-for-Teachers-and-Students.aspx?Page=2>
- [103] Levitt, H. M., McLeod, J. O. H. N., & Stiles, W. B. (2021). The conceptualization, design, and evaluation of qualitative methods in research on psychotherapy. Bergin and *Garfield's handbook of psychotherapy and behavior change*, 51-86.
- [104] Liang et al. (2021) Prevalence of anxiety and depression during COVID-19 pandemic among healthcare students in Jordan and its effect on their learning process: *national survey*. April 5, 2021 PLOS ONE.
- [105] Lomba Logan, R. M., Johnson, C. E., & Worsham, J. W. (2021). Development of an e learning module to facilitate student learning and outcomes. *Teaching and Learning in Nursing handbook*, 16(2), 139-142.
- [106] Lombardo, A. M., Andolfi, C., Deshpande, A. P., Aizen, J. M., Dangle, P. P., & Gundeti, M. S. (2021). Pediatric urology amidst SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: Building the future with current knowledge. *Journal of Pediatric Surgery*, 56(5), 923-928.
- [107] Lowes, L., & Prowse, M. A. (2017). Standing outside the interview process? The illusion of objectivity in phenomenological data generation. *International journal of nursing studies*, 38(4), 471-480.
- [108] Luchetti, M., Lee, J. H., Aschwanden, D., Sesker, A., Strickhouser, J. E., Terracciano, A., & Sutin, A. R. (2020). The trajectory of loneliness in response to COVID-19. *American Psychologist*, 75(7), 897.
- [109] Madigan, D.J., Curran, T. (2020). Does burnout affect academic achievement? A meta analysis of over 100,000 students *Educ. Psychol. Rev.*, pp. 1-19.

- [110] Magomedov, A., Khaliev, M., Khubolov, S. (2020). The negative and positive impact of the pandemic on education. *The negative and positive impact of the pandemic on education*. <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/17426596/1691/1/012134/p>.
- [111] Mallillin, L., Mallillin, D., Lipayon, I., Mallillin, J., Dayanara, M. (2021). Behavior and Attitude of Students in the New Normal Perspective of Learning. *American Psychologist*. 10.36349/easjpbs.2021.v03i02.001.
- [112] Maramot, M. B., Macaria, M. L. J. C. B., Carandang, C. C., Ilaio, R. S. C. L. V., Mendoza, G. M. L. R. A., Tolentino, J. J. M. E. R., & Ularte, M. B. (2021). CoverageCID (Connect, Innovate, Deliver): *Curriculum Implementation Advancement in SDO Batangas Province*.
- [113] Marker, H. J., & Fink, A. S. (2017). 2 CESSDA—a History of Research Data Management for Social Science Data. *Research Data Management-A European Perspective*, 25.
- [114] Martin, F., & Bolliger, D. U. (2018). Engagement matters: Student perceptions on the importance of engagement strategies in the online learning environment. *Online Learning*, 22(1), 205-222.
- [115] Marwa Mohamed Zalat, Mona Sami Hamed, Sarah Abdelhalim Bolbol (2021). The experiences, challenges, and acceptance of e-learning as a tool for teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic among university medical staff/jour <https://nals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371/journal.pone.0248758>. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0248758>.
- [116] Milia, A. M. R., Diliberto, S., Di Piazza, A., & Ingoglia, S. (2021). Psychological Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Italian University Students: A Qualitative Study using Focus Group. *Journal of Clinical & Developmental Psychology*, 3(2).
- [117] Miller, T. (2009). Formative computer-based assessment in higher education: the effectiveness of feedback in supporting student learning. *Assessment and Evaluation in Higher Education*, 34(2), 181-192.
- [118] Mirahmadzadeh, A., Ranjbar, K., Shahriarirad, R., Erfani, A., Ghaem, H., Jafari, K., Rahimi, T. (2020). Evaluation of students' attitude and emotion towards the sudden closure of schools during the COVID-19 pandemic: a cross-sectional study. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-020-00500-7>.
- [119] Mishra, L., Gupta, T., & Shree, A. (2020). Online teaching-learning in higher education during lockdown period of COVID-19 pandemic. *International Journal of Educational Research Open*, 1, 100012.
- [120] Moeller, J., Brackett, M.A., Ivcevic, Z., White, A.E. (2020). High school students' feelings: discoveries from a large national survey and an experiencesampling study. *Learn. Instruct.*, 66, p. 101301.
- [121] Moeller, J., von Keyserlingk, L., Spengler, M., Gaspard, H., Lee, H. R., Yamaguchi-Pedroza, K., ... & Arum, R. (2022). Risk and protective factors of college students' psychological well-being during the COVID-19 pandemic: emotional stability, mental health, and household resources. *Aera Open*, 8, 23328584211065725.
- [122] Mohammed, A. O., Khidhir, B. A., Nazeer, A., & Vijayan, V. J. (2020). Emergency remote teaching during Coronavirus pandemic: the current trend and future directive at Middle East College Oman. *Innovative Infrastructure Solutions*, 5(3), 1-11.
- [123] Mondragon-Estrada, E., & Camacho-Zuñiga, C. (2021, December). Undergraduate's Perspective on Being an Effective Online Student During Lockdown due to COVID-19 Pandemic: An Educational Data Mining Study. In *2021 Machine Learning-Driven Digital Technologies for Educational Innovation Workshop* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- [124] Moos, D. C., & Azevedo, R. (2008). Monitoring, planning, and self-efficacy during learning with hypermedia: The impact of conceptual scaffolds. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 24(4), 1686-1706. doi:DOI:10.1016/j.chb.2007.07.001.
- [125] Morrow, T. Rodriguez, H. & King, J. (2015). Qualitative Researching. *SAGE Publications Ltd. 6 Bonhill Street London EC2A 4PU*.
- [126] Murgatroyd, D., Georgiou, A., Li, J., Pearce, C., McLeod, A., Wabe, N., Hardie, R. A., (2021). COVID-19: protocol for observational studies utilizing near real-time electronic Australian general practice data to promote effective care and best-practice policy—a design thinking approach. *Health Research Policy and Systems*, 19(1), 1-6.

- [127] Nardo, M. T. B. (2017, October 20). Modular Instruction Enhances LearnerAutonomy. *Sciepub*.<http://pubs.sciepub.com/education/5/10/3/index.html#:~:text=The%20use%20of%20modules%20is,in%20doing%20their%20individul%20tasks.&text=It%20directs%20students%20to%20practice%20or%20rehearse%20information.,To%20gain%20mastery>.
- [128] Neuman, D. (2014). Qualitative research in educational communications and technology: A brief introduction to principles and procedures. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 26(1), 69-86.
- [129] Niemi, H. M., & Kousa, P. (2020). A case study of students' and teachers' perceptions in a Finnish high school during the COVID pandemic. *International journal of technology in education and science*.
- [130] Ng, Q.X., Z.Q, M.L. Deyn, De., Lim, D.Y., Chan, H.W., Yeo, W.S. (2020). The wounded healer: a narrative review of the mental health effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on healthcare workers. *Asian J. Psychiatr.*
- [131] Ng, Q. X., De Deyn, M. L. Z. Q., Loke, W., & Chan, H. W. (2020). A framework to deal with uncertainty in the age of COVID-19. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 54, 102263.
- [132] Nguyen, L. H., Drew, D. A., Graham, M. S., Joshi, A. D., Guo, C. G., Ma, W., ... & Zhang, F. (2020). Risk of COVID-19 among front-line health-care workers and the general community: a prospective cohort study. *The Lancet Public Health*, 5(9), e475-e483.
- [133] Oberoi, R., Halsall, J. P., & Snowden, M. (2021). Reinventing social entrepreneurship leadership in the COVID-19 era: engaging with the new normal. *Entrepreneurship Education*, 4(2), 117-136.
- [134] Oguntade, F. M. (2021). Content analysis of levels and aspects of comprehension in West African senior secondary school examination. *Reading & Writing*, 12(1), 1-10.
- [135] Okebukola, P. A., Suwadu, B., Oladejo, A., Nyandwi, R., Ademola, I., Okorie, H., & Awaah, F. (2020). Delivering high school Chemistry during COVID- 19 lockdown: Voices from Africa. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 97(9), 3285-289.
- [136] Palinkas, L. A., Horwitz, S. M., Green, C. A., Wisdom, J. P., Duan, N., & Hoagwood, K. (2015). Purposeful sampling for qualitative data collection and analysis in mixed method implementation research. *Administration and policy in mental health and mental health services research*, 42(5), 533-544.
- [137] Pan, X., Chen, D., Xia, Y., Wu, X., Li, T., Xueting Ou, Liyang Zhou, Jing Liu (2020) Asymptomatic cases in a family cluster with SARS-CoV-2 infection. *Lancet Infect. Dis.*, 20 (4), pp. 410-411.
- [138] Pandey, P., & Pandey, M. M. (2021). Research methodology tools and techniques. *Bridge Center*, 57(7), 7896-6785.
- [139] Panunciar, D. M., Bacolod, M. M., Abadiano, M. N., & Deocares, M. S. (2020). Emerging School Leadership amidst Covid-19 Pandemic. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 57(9), 5935-5963.
- [140] Park, S. H., & Kim, Y. (2018). Ways of coping with excessive academic stress among Korean adolescents during leisure time. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies on Health and Well-Being*, 13(1), 1505397.
- [141] Pattermann, J., Pammer, M., Schlögl, S., & Gstrein, L. (2022). Perceptions of Digital Device Use and Accompanying Digital Interruptions in Blended Learning. *Education Sciences*, 12(3), 215.
- [142] Patton, S. (2012). The Nature of Research: Using Research to Inspire Practice, *Centre for Educational Research and Innovation*. 7(9),
- [143] Paul, J., & Jefferson, F. (2019). A Comparative Analysis of Student Performance in an Online vs. Face-to-Face Environmental Science Course From 2009 to 2016. *Frontiers in Computer Science*, 1(7).
- [144] Peimani, N., & Kamalipour, H. (2021). Online education and the COVID-19 outbreak: A case study of online teaching during lockdown. *Education Sciences*, 11(2), 72.
- [145] Penamora, A. M. (2021). MI O Lm: Stories of Mobile Legend Gamers in Accomplishing their Learning Modules Amidst Covid-19 Pandemic: A Case Study. *International Journal of Discoveries and Innovations in Applied Sciences*, 1(7), 17-35.

- [146] Petrie, K., & Norman, A. (2020). Assessing the economic implications of coronavirus and Brexit. London: *Social Market Foundation*.
- [147] Pham, T., & Nguyen, H. (2020). COVID-19: Challenges and opportunities for Vietnamese higher education. *Higher Education in Southeast Asia and beyond*, 8, 22–24.
- [148] Pope, D. (2020). Student Reflections During the Pandemic: An Opportunity for Educators to Create a “New” Normal. <https://challengesuccess.org/resources/create-a-new-normal/>
- [149] Pokhrel, S., Chhetri, R. (2021). A Literature Review on Impact of COVID-19 Pandemic on Teaching and Learning. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2347631120983481>
- [150] Pople, D. (2021). Student stress during the pandemic. <https://ed.stanford.edu/news/student-stress-during-pandemic>.
- [151] Pradhan, P., Subedi, D. R., Khatiwada, D., Joshi, K. K., Kafle, S., Chhetri, R. P., ... & Bhujju, D. R. (2021). The COVID-19 Pandemic Not Only Poses Challenges, but Also Opens Opportunities for Sustainable Transformation. *Earth's Future*, 9(7), e2021EF001996.
- [152] Prakriti, R. (2021). Can COVID-19 Have a Positive Impact on Education? <https://www.smilefoundationindia.org/blog/can-covid-19have-a-positive-impact-on-education/>.
- [153] Prime, H., Wade, M., & Browne, D. T. (2020). Risk and resilience in family well being during the COVID-19 pandemic. *American Psychologist*, 75(5), 631.
- [154] Putra, P., Liriwati, F. Y., Tahrim, T., Syafrudin, S., & Aslan, A. (2020). The students learning from home experience during covid-19 school closures policy in indonesia. *Journal Iqra*, 5(2).
- [155] Qian, W. A. N. G. (2015). A study of the influence of gender differences on English learning of senior high school students. *Higher Education of Social Science*, 8(6), 66-69.
- [156] Rachman, L. A., Sudiyono, S., & Phonix, E. (2021). The Blended Learning Implementation of ELT Based on Teachers and Students Perspective in New Normal Condition of COVID 19. *Project (Professional Journal of English Education)*, 4(3), 457-468.
- [157] Rafferty, K. A. (2015). "Everything remains uncertain": Theorizing parents' communication about uncertainty, hope, and hopelessness while managing complex pediatric chronic conditions (*Doctoral dissertation, The University of Wisconsin-Milwaukee*).
- [158] Rafferty, A. N., LaMar, M. M., & Griffiths, T. L. (2015). Inferring learners' knowledge from their actions. *Cognitive Science*, 39(3), 584-618.
- [159] Raharjo, J. S. D., Hendartho, D., Susanti, E., & Ekasari, R. (2021). Changes of Learning Communication Models in New Normal Adaptation: From Classroom Learning to Distance Learning Environment. *IJomata International Journal of Management*, 2(4), 309-318.
- [160] Rahmanti, A. R., Ningrum, D. N. A., Lazuardi, L., Yang, H. C., & Li, Y. C. J. (2021). Social media data analytics for outbreak risk communication: public attention on the “New Normal” during the COVID-19 pandemic in Indonesia. *Computer Methods and Programs in Biomedicine*, 205, 106083.
- [161] Raja, M., & Lakshmi Priya, G. G. (2022). Using virtual reality and augmented reality with ICT tools for enhancing quality in the changing academic environment in COVID-19 pandemic: An empirical study. In *Technologies, Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Learning Post-COVID-19* (pp. 467-482). Springer, Cham.
- [162] Ratten, V. (2020). Coronavirus (Covid-19) and the entrepreneurship education community. *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*.
- [163] Rawat, K., Kumari, P., & Saha, L. (2021). COVID-19 vaccine: A recent update in pipeline vaccines, their design and development strategies. *European journal of pharmacology*, 892, 173751.
- [164] RDO, A. M., Andolfi, C., Deshpande, A. P., Aizen, J. M., Dangle, P. P., & Gundeti, M.S. (2021). Pediatric urology amidst SARS-CoV-2 pandemic: Building the future with current knowledge. *Journal of Pediatric Surgery*, 56(5), 923-928.

- [165] Reimers, F., Schleicher, A., Saavedra, J., & Tuominen, S. (2020). Supporting the continuation of teaching and learning during the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Oecd*, 1(1), 1-38.
- [166] Renström, E. A., & Bäck, H. (2021). Emotions during the Covid-19 pandemic: Fear, anxiety, and anger as mediators between threats and policy support and political actions. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 51(8), 861-877.
- [167] Roediger III, H. L., Putnam, A. L., & Smith, M. A. (2017). Ten benefits of testing and their applications to educational practice. *Psychology of learning and motivation*, 55, 1-36
- [168] Rotas, E. E., & Cahapay, M. B. (2020). Difficulties in Remote Learning: Voices of Philippine University Students in the Wake of COVID-19 Crisis. *Asian Journal of Distance Education*, 15(2), 147-158.
- [169] Rume, T., & Islam, S. D. U. (2020). Environmental effects of COVID-19 pandemic and potential strategies of sustainability. *Heliyon*, 6(9), e04965.
- [170] Quinn, C. N. (2011). Designing mLearning: Tapping into the mobile revolution for organizational performance. *John Wiley & Sons*.
- [171] Rutzler, S. (2020). Importance of Reading Comprehension. <https://www.mathgenie.com/blog/importance-of-readingcomprehension>.
- [172] Satyarthi, S. (2017). An effective learning strategy for secondary school students' modular approach. *ZENITH International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 7(1), 44-52.
- [173] Sadeghi, M. (2019). A shift from classroom to distance learning: Advantages and limitations. *International Journal of Research in English Education*, 4(1), 80- 88.
- [174] Sapkota, K. R. (2021). An Evaluation Framework to Measure and Evaluate the Outputs, Outcomes and Impact of Third Mission Initiatives and Social Impact Programs of Kings College (Nepal). *Journal Research in Science*, 7(2), 40-42.
- [175] Scoffham, S., & Barnes, J. (2011). Happiness matters: towards a pedagogy of happiness and well-being. *Curriculum Journal*, 22(4), 535-548.
- [176] Sharma, C. (2022). A Study on the Effect of COVID-19 towards the perception of Government Inter College Teachers in Dehradun District. *Journal of Positive School Psychology*, 4894-4908.
- [177] Shelviana, A. S., & Sunarno, W. (2020, September). A Needs Analysis of Problem-Based Physic Modules of Senior High School. In *Proceedings of the 4th International Conference on Learning Innovation and Quality Education* (pp. 1-5).
- [178] Shen, L., Dillard, J. P., & Peng, L. (2022). Correspondence between Two Methods of Measuring Discrete Emotions: Self-report versus Machine-coded Facial Displays. *Western Journal of Communication*, 1-21.
- [179] Shen, P., Lee, T., & Tsai, C. (2008). Enhancing skills of application software via web-enabled problem-based learning and self-regulated learning: an exploratory study. *International journal of distance education technologies*, 6(3), 69.
- [180] Simbulan, N. (2020). COVID-19 and its impact on higher education in the Philippines. *Higher Education in Southeast Asia and beyond*, 8, 15-18.
- [181] Sintema, E. J. (2020). Effect of COVID-19 on the performance of grade 12 students: Implications for STEM education. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 16(7), em1851.
- [182] Sparrow, R., Dartanto, T., & Hartwig, R. (2020). Indonesia under the new normal: Challenges and the way ahead. *Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies*, 56(3), 269-299.
- [183] Stevens, G. J., Bienz, T., Wali, N., Condie, J., & Schismenos, S. (2021). Online university education is the new normal: but is face-to-face better?. *Interactive Technology and Smart Education*.
- [184] Stracke, C. M., Burgos, D., Santos-Hermosa, G., Bozkurt, A., Sharma, R. C., Swiatek Cassafieres, C., & Truong, V. (2022). Responding to the initial challenge of the COVID-19 pandemic: Analysis of international responses and impact in school and higher education. *Sustainability*, 14(3), 1876.

- [185] Surmiak, A. (2018, September). Confidentiality in qualitative research involving vulnerable participants: Researchers' perspectives. In Forum: *Qualitative Social Research (Vol. 19, No. 3, pp. 393-418)*. Freie Universität Berlin.
- [186] Sutton, J., & Austin, Z. (2015). Qualitative research: Data collection, analysis, and management. *The Canadian journal of hospital pharmacy*, 68(3), 226.
- [187] Taunan, M., Barcelona, S. R. D., Sandoval, R. N. P., & Flaviano, R. L. (2021). Lived Experiences of the Senior High School Learners at Goshen School of Technology and Humanities During the Covid 19 Pandemic. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary: Applied Business and Education Research*, 2(6), 479-484.
- [188] Thomas, S. P. (2021). Resolving tensions in phenomenological research interviewing. *Journal of Advanced Nursing*, 77(1), 484-491.
- [189] Thompson, C. N., Baumgartner, J., Pichardo, C., Toro, B., Li, L., Arciuolo, R., & Fine, A. (2020). COVID-19 Outbreak—New York City, February 29–June 1, 2020. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report*, 69(46), 1725.
- [190] Tipon, F. K., Villanueva, A., Juan, M. B. K. L. M., Cruz, N. D., & Tus, J. (2021). The Self-Efficacy and its Relationship to the Academic Motivation of the Senior High School Students from Public Schools Amidst the New Normal Education in the Philippines: *International Journal Of Advance Research And Innovative Ideas In Education*.
- [191] Tolley, E. E., Ulin, P. R., Mack, N., Robinson, E. T., & Succop, S. M. (2016). Qualitative methods in public health: *a field guide for applied research*. John Wiley & Sons, 3-5.
- [192] Tubadji, A. (2021). Culture and mental health resilience in times of COVID-19. *Journal of Population Economics*, 34(4), 1219-1259.
- [193] Tus, J. (2020). Self-Concept, Self-Esteem, Self-Efficacy and Academic Performance of the Senior High School Students. *International Journal of Research Culture Society*, 4(10).
- [194] Tria, J. Z. (2020). The COVID-19 pandemic through the lens of education in the Philippines: The new normal. *International Journal of Pedagogical Development and Lifelong Learning*, 1(1), 2-4.
- [195] UNESCO. (2020). COVID-19 Educational disruption and response. <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-emergencies/coronavirus-school-closures> accessed 27 February 2021.
- [196] Van Manen, M., & van Manen, M. (2021). Doing phenomenological research and writing. *Qualitative Health Research*, 31(6), 1069-1082
- [197] Veale, J. F., Deutsch, M. B., Devor, A. H., Kuper, L. E., Motmans, J., Radix, A. E., & Amand, C. S. (2022). Setting a research agenda in trans health: An expert assessment of priorities and issues by trans and nonbinary researchers. *International Journal of Transgender Health*, 1-17.
- [198] Wall, K., & Jose, J. S. (2017). Managing work and care: A difficult challenge for immigrant families. *Social policy & administration*, 38(6), 591-621.
- [199] Wang, Y., Jing, X., Han, W., Jing, Y., & Xu, L. (2020). Positive and negative affect of university and college students during COVID-19 outbreak: a network-based survey. *International journal of public health*, 65(8), 1437-1443.
- [200] Wang, C. W., Sainz, A., Joshi, S. C., & Alfred, M. V. (2022). A case study of adult education and literacy programs and the transition to remote services during the COVID-19 pandemic. *New Horizons in Adult Education and Human Resource Development*, 34(1), 37-50.
- [201] World Health Organization. (2018). *World health statistics 2018: monitoring health for the SDGs, sustainable development goals*. World Health Organization.
- [202] World Health Organization, (2018) Coronavirus disease (COVID-2019) situation reports. *WorldHealthStatistics*. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/situation-reports>.
- [203] Williams, S. N., Armitage, C. J., Tampe, T., & Dienes, K. (2020). Public perceptions and experiences of social distancing and social isolation during the COVID-19 pandemic: A UK-based focus group study. *BMJ open*, 10(7), e039334.

- [204] William, E. (2021). Back to School amidst the New Normal: Ongoing Effects of the Coronavirus Pandemic on Children's Health and Well-Being. *Applied Psychology*, 56(8), 345-347.
- [205] Williams, H. (2021). The Meaning of "Phenomenology": Qualitative and Philosophical Phenomenological Research Methods. *The Qualitative Report*, 26(2), 366-385.
- [206] Winne, P. (2005). Key issues in modeling and applying research on self-regulated learning. *Applied Psychology*, 54(2), 232-238.
- [207] Winne, P. (2006). How software technologies can improve research on learning and bolsterschool reform. *Educational psychologist*, 41(1), 5-17.
- [208] Xie, X., Siau, K., & Nah, F. F. H. (2020). COVID-19 pandemic—online education in the new normal and the next normal. *Journal of information technology case and application research*, 22(3), 175-187.
- [209] Yassine, F. L. Y. A., Maaitah, T. A., Maaitah, D. A., & Al-Gasawneh, J. A. (2022). Impact of COVID-19 on the University Education System in Jordan. *Journal of Southwest Jiaotong University*, 57(1).
- [210] Yildirim, M., Arslan, G., & Wong, P. T. (2021). Meaningful living, resilience, affective balance, and psychological health problems among Turkish young adults during coronavirus pandemic. *Current Psychology*, 1-12.
- [211] Zalat, M. M., Hamed, M. S., & Bolbol, S. A. (2021). The experiences, challenges, and acceptance of e-learning as a tool for teaching during the COVID-19 pandemic among university medical staff. *Plos One*, 16(3), e0248758.
- [212] Zhai, Y., & Du, X. (2020). Mental health care for international Chinese student affected by the COVID-19 outbreak. *The Lancet Psychiatry*, 7(4), e22
- [213] Zimmerman, B. J. (2017). Motivational sources and outcomes of self-regulated learning and performance: Graduate center of city university of new york. *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance* (pp. 63-78). Routledge